

Nano Rectangular Dielectric Resonator Antenna for Terahertz Applications

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Abstract: The paper describes a novel method for increasing gain on a Nano RDRA using a Teflon substrate. The results of the enhanced gain are analysed and compared to previous research work. A Nano RDRA was designed and simulated using CST software. At a frequency of 500THz, the antenna structure contains rectangular dielectric resonators with higher antenna gain. The Nano RDRA has a 9.37% impedance bandwidth. The reported Nano RDRA has a gain of 4.56 dB and an efficiency of 54.25%. Terahertz applications are possible with the proposed Nano RDRA.

Index Terms - Nano Antenna, Rectangular DRA, High gain and Terahertz band.

I. INTRODUCTION

The dielectric resonator antenna has high speed of advantages as easy fabrication, cheaper cost and small in size [1][2]. The article shows dielectric resonator antennas with slot are applicable in wireless communication [3]. Ceramic is commonly used in dielectric resonators; however, in the microwave range, losses in the ceramic material increase due to interactions between the applied field and photons, causing the optical lattice vibrations to be dampened [4]. As a result, sapphire outperforms ceramic materials in terms of performance [5]. The DRAs outperformed traditional radio lines such as mono poles, dipoles, and tiny size strip fix reception devices in their tests [6]. Around the same time, researchers used the DR material to construct a planar cluster of circularly polarized receiving wire arrays [7]. According to these experts' findings, DRA is an open reverberating structure that uses the dielectric resonator (DR) as a transmission mechanism, with its resonant frequency determined by its estimates and permittivity [8]. Analysts' attention shifted in the late 1990s to the construction of planar and straight arrays with DRAs [9]. A variety of DRAs using the miniaturized size strip feed were constructed in order to build a dielectric receiving device display using gap coupling [10]. The researchers developed a collection of circularly captivated and staged DRA. There is growing interest in dielectric resonator antennas because they have many advantages over other types of antennas, such as small size, lightweight, and low cost [11]. The rectangular dielectric resonator antenna (RDRA) is simple to construct, and one or more than one-dimensional variables are available as additional degrees of freedom for the designer [12]. The obtained resonant frequency and the two RDRA aspect ratios (length/height and length/width) can be chosen independently [13]. This antenna shape allows for greater control over bandwidth [14]. The most common shape of DRA is rectangular DRA. DRA's fundamental shape is extremely adaptable [15]. In comparison to metallic antennas, DR antennas have the advantage of operating at a constant frequency from microwave to optical [16]. The rectangular shape of a micro antenna provides a larger exposed surface area than cylindrical or spherical DRA forms [17].

II. ANTENNA DESIGN

Antennas are the foundation of wireless communication, and without them, the world would not be where it is today. The first section functions as a transmitter, converting direct current electricity to microwaves via a transmitting circuit and a transmitting antenna. Microwaves are sent through the antenna, which travels across free space to the third block's receiver. The receiver converts microwaves to alternating current (AC) electricity using the receiving antenna. The rectifying circuit is then used to convert the collected alternating current power back to direct current. As a result, they are named after the major components of a rectenna. After the RF filter has routed the AC power as far away from the antenna as possible, the collected AC power is converted to DC using a diode (i.e., a Schottky diode). A DC filter is installed after the diode to ensure that no AC power reaches the load. The DC filter is mostly made up of a shunt capacitor that acts as a short circuit at higher frequencies. A resistive load then consumes the DC power. Nearby mobile phones can be used to collect RF energy. The labeled top view of the Nano RDRA is given in figure and the labeled side view of the Nano RDRA is given in figure 2. Table I shows the Design dimensions of Nano RDRA.

Figure. 1: Labeled top view of the Nano RDRA

Figure. 2: Labeled side view of the Nano RDRA

Table-I Design dimensions of Nano RDRA

S. No	NAME	MATERIAL USED		L (nm)	W (nm)	H (nm)
1	GROUND PLANE	SILVER	1	900	900	100
2	SUBSTRATE	TEFLON-BASED	2.08	900	900	100
3	MICROSTRIP NANO FEED	SILVER	1	450	67	10
4	RECTANGULAR DR	TITANIUM DIOXIDE	8.29	128	128	60
5	VACCUM SHEET	VACCUM	1	1500	1500	1200

III. FORMULATIONS

The aim of this section is to present a calculation involving the computation of the quantum statistical moments of the electromagnetic field produced by an ensemble of electrons and positrons whose state is specified by a mixed state superposition of Fermionic Coherent states. Fermionic Coherent states are parameterized by Grassmannian, Fermionic numbers and to attach physical significance to the final results, we must use the Berezin integral for Fermionic variables to determine the below mentioned superposition of Fermionic coherent states.

First consider just a single Fermion specified by the annihilation operator a and the creation operator a^* . Thus,

$$a^2 = a^{*2} = 0, \quad aa^* + a^*a = 1$$

In such a cube, the solutions to the Maxwell equations come from

$$A_r(t, x, y, z) = \sum_{mnp} c(mnp, t) u_{r, mnp}(x, y, z), \quad r = 1, 2, 3$$

Where $u_{r, mnp}$ are spatial functions obtained by integrating the electric field w. r. t

$$\left\{ \cos\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right), \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{a}\right) \right\} \otimes \left\{ \cos\left(\frac{n\pi y}{a}\right), \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{a}\right) \right\} \otimes \left\{ \cos\left(\frac{p\pi z}{a}\right), \sin\left(\frac{p\pi z}{a}\right) \right\}$$

Multiplied by a number of constants based on the indices We can assume, without losing generality, that are normalized in such a way that

$$\int_c u_{r, mnp}(r) \bar{u}_{s, m'n'p'}(r) d^3r = \delta_{rs} \delta_{mm'} \delta_{nn'} \delta_{pp'}$$

The dependence of $c(mnp, t)$ on t is $\exp(i\omega(mnp)t)$ where $\omega(mnp)$ are the characteristic frequencies of oscillation:

$$\omega(mnp) = \left(\frac{\pi c}{a}\right) \sqrt{m^2 + n^2 + p^2}, \quad m, n, p = 1, 2, \dots$$

Which are of the order of magnitude

$$\omega = \frac{\pi c}{a}$$

The electric field is

$$E_r = \partial_t A_r = \sum_{mnp} c(mnp, t) i\omega(mnp) u_r, mnp(r)$$

The magnetic field is

$$B = curl A$$

Which is of the magnitude $\frac{|c(mnp,t)|}{a}$ where $c(mnp, t)$ we actually mean its average in a coherent state. Within the cavity C, the total electric field energy is

$$U_E = \left(\frac{\epsilon_0}{2}\right) \int_C |E|^2 d^3r$$

The magnitude of the pointing vector corresponding to the power emitted by the Dirac field in the distant field zone is then

$$S \approx c \left(\epsilon_0 E^2 + \frac{B^2}{\mu_0} \right) = c^3 \epsilon_0 \omega^2 e a^3 + e^2 c^3 a / \mu_0$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The given below figure 3 to figure 9 are design and simulation results of Nano RDRA. Each graph has its citation describing the name of the parameters such as Smith chart, Radiation pattern, S11, Gain, Efficiency, E- field and H-field of Quantum RDRA at 500 THz.

Fig. 3 Smith Chart of Nano RDRA

Fig. 4 Radiation pattern Nano RDRA

Fig. 5 Return loss Nano RDRA

Fig. 6 Gain Nano RDRA

Fig. 7 Efficiency of Nano RDRA

Fig. 8 E field of Nano RDRA

Fig. 9 H field of Nano RDRA

Table II Comparison with the other THz antennas

Ref.	10 dB Impedance bandwidth (THz)	Gain (dB)	Efficiency (%)
[18]	0.7 – 0.85	3.502	55.88
[19]	1.84 – 2.42	3.9	100
[20]	0.42 – 0.48	0.13	24
[21]	0.924 – 1.2	2	44
[22]	4.0629 – 4.1299	3.8	72 – 75
Proposed	474.44 - 521.11	4.56	54.25

Table II shows the comparison between the proposed Nano RDRA and the THz antennas in the references. The Nano RDRA has a higher impedance bandwidth and a wider gain. The Nano RDRA has excellent radiation properties.

V. CONCLUSION

A nano strip feed DRA-based antenna has been created for the THz frequency band. The 500 THz frequency of Nano RDRA was chosen for potential high-speed communication applications. The rectangular shape of the design makes it straightforward; the use of DR makes it effective; and the use of Teflon as a radiator makes it unique. The wireless TBPS data transfer using these antennas might be advantageous. Nano RDRA ought to be compact and power efficient.

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